

STUDIES ON THIOSEMICARBAZONES. PART I

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Certain derivatives of *p*-aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone have been prepared and their chemical characteristics described.

Behnisch, Mietzsch and Schmidt, working in collaboration with Donagk, have found (*Naturwiss.*, 1946, 33, 315) in *p*-aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone (I) an agent active against tubercule bacilli. Acylation leads to a more effective compound (cf. Behnisch, Mietzsch and Schmidt, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1948, 60, 113); but the activity is found first to increase and then decrease with higher acyl groupings. It is to be further noted that neither the free aldehyde group, nor the free thiosemicarbazide is responsible for its chemotherapeutic action. The activity is also not inhibited by the presence of *p*-aminobenzoic acid. The compound may, however, undergo a tautomeric change as follows:

The prototropic change involved in the formation of the conjugated system (II) may induce an enhanced activity in the compound (cf. Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc., Ind. & News Ed.*, 1950, 13, 167). The aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone by its condensation with an aldehyde would form compounds of azomethine structure (III), where the mobility of the hydrogen may be further enhanced and thereby lead to the formation of a more active compound. As a matter of fact, the observations of Behnisch *et al.* (*Amer. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1950, 61, 1) tend to indicate in the above direction. On this hypothesis, some derivatives of azomethines of the type (III) have been prepared by reacting *p*-aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone with benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde and cinnamic aldehyde, and are described in the experimental part of the paper.

The compound, *p*-aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone, also breaks down into the body into aminobenzaldehyde and thiosemicarbazide, and gives rise to some toxic reactions; prevention of rapid systemic absorption may offer a product of low toxicity. For this, the amino grouping in (I) has been acylated with phthalic anhydride under conditions recorded in this paper (cf. Basu and Banerjee, *Science & Culture*, 1951, 16, 331). The paper is based on a pending patent application.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Benzilidene-aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone.—*p*-Aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone (2 g.) was refluxed in 25 c.c. rectified spirit with benzaldehyde (1.2 g.)

for one hour. The resulting solution on cooling afforded the benzilidene compound. It was filtered and washed with alcohol, yield 2.5 g., yellow crystals (from alcohol), m.p. 181°. (Found: N, 20.05. $C_{18}H_{14}N_4S$ requires N, 19.86 per cent). The compound in alcoholic solution is desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury on warming and it also forms a fine yellow double salt with mercuric chloride.

p-Salicylidene-aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone.—*p*-Aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone (2.1 g.) was dissolved in 30 c.c. alcohol (95%) and refluxed for ten minutes with salicylaldehyde (1.8 g.). The yellow salicylidene compound obtained was crystallised from alcohol in plates, m.p. 207-8°, yield 2.9 g. The compound is sparingly soluble in alcohol and acetone, fairly soluble in cold dilute alkali, insoluble in cold dilute acid but goes in solution on boiling. (Found: N, 18.46. $C_{18}H_{14}ON_4S$ requires N, 18.79 per cent). This compound also readily forms a complex with mercuric chloride in alcoholic solution, but is not so susceptible to desulphurisation by mercuric oxide.

p-Cinnamylidene-aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone.—*p*-Aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone (2 g.) in 30 c.c. rectified spirit was similarly refluxed with 1.5 g. of cinnamic aldehyde for 1 hour, when a yellow product was formed, which was isolated in the usual way and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 203°-4°, yield 2.5 g. The compound is insoluble in water but moderately soluble in hot alcohol and acetone; it dissolves in acids on boiling. (Found: N, 18.35. $C_{17}H_{14}N_4S$ requires N, 18.18 per cent). No change was noticed on boiling its alcoholic solution in presence of yellow mercuric oxide; but the compound readily formed the complex with mercuric chloride.

p-Phthalylaminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone.—*p*-Aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone (2 g.) in 50 c.c. acetone was refluxed with freshly sublimed phthalic anhydride (2 g.). The resulting phthalyl derivative was filtered off and washed with cold alcohol and purified by dissolving it in sodium bicarbonate solution (charcoal) and allowing it to stand for ten minutes and then filtering and precipitating the filtrate with dilute acetic acid, m.p. 222-23° (decomp.), yield 2.2 g. The same reaction might be brought about by dissolving the *p*-aminobenzaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone in chloroform and pyridine and then adding cautiously a slight excess of phthalyl chloride (b.p. 276°) without allowing the temperature to rise. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for some time, cooled and diluted with water. The phthalyl derivative was filtered off, washed with water and alcohol, m.p. 222-23° (decomp.). (Found: N, 16.91. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2N_4$ requires N, 16.37 per cent).

This compound is very sparingly soluble in hot alcohol and acetone; insoluble in water but dissolves in aqueous solution of alkali carbonate, bicarbonate and caustic alkalies. It is unchanged by dilute acids but dissolves in 60% sulphuric acid on warming. The acid solution forms a green coloration with copper sulphate solution. The reaction with mercuric chloride was slow and no change was noticed when heated with mercuric oxide (yellow) in alcoholic suspension.

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